

The plasma-induced leukemia cell death is dictated by the ROS chemistry and the HO-1/CXCL8 axis

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Abstract—Cold physical plasma-derived ROS inactivate cells, which might be beneficial in oncology. However, several aspects of plasma oncotherapy remain elusive. These include the identification of a ROS composition with maximum toxicity and the molecular mechanisms that govern the degree of plasma-induced cell death. Using two human leukemia cell lines and the plasma jet kINPen, we identified Jurkat cells to be most sensitive to argon plasma while THP-1 cells were most sensitive to He/O₂ plasma. Screening of 20 protein transcripts involved in redox regulation identified HMOX1 as a commonly regulated element, and siRNA-mediated knockdown of the HMOX1-transcribed protein HO-1 augmented plasma-derived cell death in the two leukemia cell lines. Interestingly, knockdown of the H₂O₂-decomposing enzyme catalase did not elevate plasma-induced cell death. By contrast, siRNA-mediated suppression of the production of the chemokine CXCL8 (IL8) markedly enhanced plasma-derived cytotoxicity up to two-fold. Vice versa, by antibody-mediated blocking of IL8 receptors, a massive increase in IL8 and HO-1 secretion was observed, together with a dramatically enhanced cell death in response to plasma treatment, especially in THP-1 cells. These results suggest that the plasma-induced leukemia cell death is dictated by the ROS chemistry and the HO-1/CXCL8 axis via paracrine or autocrine IL8-mediated pro-survival signaling.

Index Terms—IL8; Jurkat; HMOX1; kINPen; oncology; plasma medicine; THP-1

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I. INTRODUCTION

Cold physical plasma is a partially ionized gas that is currently used as an accredited medical procedure to support wound healing in Europe [1]. Besides its documented antimicrobial and stimulating effects in skin cells [2, 3], emerging evidence in the last decade also pointed to a potent tumor-toxicity with extended plasma treatment [4, 5]. To date, plasma exposure was shown to inactivate cancer cells of various origins, including the pancreas [6-8], leukemia [9-11], breast [12-14], ovarian [15-17], colon [18-20], skin [21-23], head and neck [24-26], and the brain [27-29]. First patients suffering from stage IV head and neck squamous cell carcinoma have benefited from plasma therapy in a palliative setting [30-32].

Many preclinical studies and first clinical evidence appear promising, but the molecular basis of plasma-mediated tumor toxicity is less clear. It is understood that the primary mechanism of action by which gas plasmas target cells and tissues is the loco-regional deposition of a plethora of reactive oxygen species (ROS) generated during plasma treatment [33]. Currently, the holy grail of plasma medicine is the identification of the optimal ROS mixture that maximizes tumor-toxic effects. While plasma systems using the ambient air, such as many dielectric barrier discharges, can be controlled mostly by their electrical parameters, the majority of plasma jets utilize noble gases such as helium and argon [34]. Such plasma jets can be modulated elegantly by admixing molecular gases such as O₂

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Figure 1. The optimal cytotoxic feed gas composition differed depending on the cell type investigated. (a) image of the plasma treatment setup; (b) representative image of the resazurin assay used to investigate the metabolic activity that correlates with the pink color of the transformed resorufin; (c, d) metabolic activity of Jurkat cells (c) and THP-1 cells (d) 4 h after exposure to plasma with different feed gas combinations and fluxes (0.5-2.0 slm) for 10 s and 30 s for each cell type, respectively; (e) representative fluorescence microscopy images indicative of apoptosis (green) and terminal cell death (blue) in both Jurkat and THP-1 cells at 6 h after plasma treatment of one experiment; (f, g) metabolic activity of Jurkat, SKM, and THP-1 cells 24h after argon (f) or He/O₂ (g) plasma treatment for 20s and 40s, respectively. Data represent mean and S.E. of three independent experiments; statistical analysis was performed using two-way analysis of variances with Dunnett posthoc testing against argon (c) or He/O₂ (d), or one-way analysis of variances (f, g); * = p<0.05, ** = p<0.01, *** = p<0.001; the scale bar is 100 μm; n.s. = not significant, slm = standard liters per minute, Ar = argon, He = helium, SKM = SK-MEL-28; § indicates the most toxic feed gas composition for each Jurkat and THP-1 cells, respectively.

and N₂. This way, the ROS composition can be shifted towards control of, for instance, nitric oxide, atomic oxygen, and hydroxyl radical production [35, 36]. While many studies,

including our own, have successfully attempted to optimize the feed gas for maximum toxicity [37-41], evidence on its broad applicability across several cell lines is scarce. Along similar

lines, several reports noted differences in the sensitivity of different cancer lines towards plasma treatment, but the underlying molecular mechanisms related to plasma-derived ROS and its cell death induction remain largely elusive.

To decipher both optimal plasma-derived ROS compositions as well as cellular proteins dictating the sensitivity of cells to the plasma-induced cell death, we utilized an atmospheric pressure plasma jet and two human leukemia cell lines Jurkat and THP-1 to tackle these challenges. Similar to their primary counterparts [42], these cell types differ in their sensitivity to plasma at a maximum degree [43, 44], allowing conclusions their sensitivity to plasma treatment in the presence or absence of target proteins. The intention was to use both cell types for a proof-of-concept study that can be extended for further cell types and plasma sources, rather than claiming a therapeutic benefit. It was found that both cell lines showed maximum sensitivity, not to a similar but different feed gas composition and that the siRNA-mediated knockdown of the proteins heme oxygenase 1 (HO-1) and interleukin 8 (IL8, also known as chemokine CXCL8) as well as receptor-blockage of the IL8-receptors (IL8R, also known as CXCR1 and CXCR2) vastly enhanced plasma-induced cytotoxicity.

II. METHODS

A. Cell culture

The human leukemia lymphocyte cell line Jurkat (ATCC TIB-152) and monocyte cell line THP-1 (ATCC TIB-202), as well as the human melanoma cell line SK-MEL-28 (SKM; ATCC HTB-72), were cultured in Roswell Park Memorial Institute (RPMI) 1640 cell culture medium supplemented with 10 % fetal bovine serum, 1% penicillin/streptomycin, and 1% glutamine (all Sigma, Germany) under standard cell culture conditions (37°C, 5 % CO₂, 95 % humidity). Cells were sub-cultured two to three times per week.

B. Plasma jet and treatment of cells

The atmospheric pressure plasma jet kINPen (neoplas tools, Germany) was utilized. It is similar in construction to the clinically accredited kINPen MED and was operated at 1MHz. The plasma jet was attached to a software-controlled, motorized xyz-table (CNC step, Germany) capable of hovering over the center of each well at a predefined jet-to-well distance with 10 μm precision. Feed gas modulation was performed using an eight-channel flow controller unit (MKS, Germany) that was factor-adjusted to each of the gases used in this study (argon, helium, oxygen, nitrogen; all >99.99% purity; Air Liquide, Germany). For treatment, 1x10⁵ viable cells in 400 μl of fully supplemented cell culture medium were added to 24-well plates and treated with each of the plasma gas conditions for either 10 s (Jurkats) or 30 s (THP-1). Viable-cell-determinations were performed with high accuracy using acoustic focusing flow cytometry (attune nxt; Applied Biosystems, USA) with dead cell exclusion via propidium iodide (PI). Feed gas addition was 1 % for oxygen and nitrogen with a bulk gas flux of argon and helium of 0.5 to 2.0 standard liters per minute (slm). At 4 h, the cells were subjected to metabolic activity analysis or pelleted

and stored at -20 °C for gene expression analysis. For transfection experiments, only argon plasma treatment was performed at 2.0 slm, and cells were analyzed 24 h later.

C. Metabolic activity, cell viability, and flow cytometry

The cells were incubated for 2h with resazurin (100μM; Alfa Aesar, USA) to determine the metabolic activity. During incubation at 37 °C, metabolically active cells reduce resazurin to its fluorescent form, resorufin. The fluorescence was quantified using a multi-mode fluorescence plate reader at λ_{ex} 535 nm and λ_{em} 590 nm (Tecan, Switzerland), and fluorescence intensities of samples were normalized against those of untreated cells for each cell line separately. For live-cell imaging experiments, the cells were incubated with CellEvent caspase 3/7 detection reagent (Thermo, USA) to identify apoptosis, and 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI; BioLegend, USA) to identify terminally dead cells. Cells were imaged at 6 h post plasma treatment using a high content imaging device (Operetta CLS; PerkinElmer, Germany) with a 20x (NA: 0.4) air objective (Zeiss, Germany) using the brightfield channel, the λ_{ex} 475nm λ_{em} 525±25 nm channel to detect fluorescence of the caspase 3/7 activation, and the λ_{ex} 405 nm λ_{em} 465±35 nm channel to detect DAPI fluorescence when bound to DNA. *Harmony* 4.9 (PerkinElmer, Germany) served as image analysis software. DAPI was also used to identify the relative distribution of cells with compromised cell membranes using flow cytometry (CytoFLEX S; Beckman-Coulter, USA). The relative expression intensities of CD181 (CXCR1) and CD182 (CXCR2) were analyzed using flow cytometry. Twenty-four hours after plasma treatment, cells were harvested, washed with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), and incubated with monoclonal antibodies conjugated with fluorochromes (anti-CD181-phycoerythrin and anti-CD182 allophycocyanin; both BioLegend, UK), before analyzing the mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) of each antibody in the viable (DAPI⁻) cell fraction. In a second setting, the cells were pre-incubated with the antibody or recombinant human interleukin (IL) 8 (100ng/ml; BioLegend, UK), followed by plasma treatment and cell viability analysis using flow cytometry 24h later. *Kaluza* 2.1.1 (Beckman-Coulter, USA) served as flow cytometry analysis software.

D. mRNA quantification

After 4 h of incubation of the untreated or plasma-treated cells, cells were taken off or scratched off the dishes and transferred into 1.5 ml tubes (Eppendorf, Germany). After pelleting and suspending in lysis buffer, RNA isolation was performed according to the manufacturer's protocol (RNA Mini Kit; Bio&SELL, Germany). The RNA concentration of each sample was measured by using the NanoDrop 2000C (Thermo, USA) device. The RNA was aliquoted into micro-tubes for further experiments. For quantitative polymerase chain reaction (qPCR), 1 μg of RNA was synthesized into cDNA according to the manufacturer's instructions (ThermoFisher, USA) using a thermocycler (Biometra, Germany). qPCR was performed in white 96-well V-bottom plates with Sybr Green (BioRad, Germany) labeled targets over 40-cycles using a Light Cycler

Figure 2. The baseline mRNA expression of 20 redox-related target proteins. (a) the expression of the target transcripts in relation to GAPDH measured for each cell line independently; (b) the expression of the target transcripts normalized to that of Jurkat cells. Data represent mean and S.E. of two independent experiments; statistical analysis was performed using two-way analysis of variances, and is shown only for gene expression above the threshold of ± 2 -fold of Jurkat expression; *** = $p < 0.001$; n.d. = none determined, SKM = SK-MEL-28.

480 machine (Roche, Switzerland). Fold changes in expression in relation to the house-keeping gene GAPDH were calculated using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$ method.

E. siRNA-mediated knockdown and protein validation

The cells were transfected with different siRNAs using an Amaxa electroporation device in combination with the Cell Line Nucleofector Kit V (Lonza, Germany). For this, 1×10^6

cells (per condition) were suspended in 100 μ l of the transfection buffer from the kit. Transfection was performed either in the absence (mock) or presence of non-targeting control (NTC: luciferase) or targeting (HMOX1, catalase, IL8) siRNA (Thermo, USA). The catalog numbers of the ESI siRNAs are EHU051241 (HMOX1), EHU048671 (catalase), and EHU048321 (IL8). Three hundred nanograms of the respective siRNA were added to the cells to be transfected using special electroporation cuvettes. After electroporation, the cell suspension was transferred to the cell culture medium and rested for 24 h at 37 °C. Western blot was performed to validate protein knockdown. For this, transfected cells were pelleted, washed, lysed, and degraded in 100 μ l of NuPAGE LDS Sample Buffer (Thermo, USA) and Dithiothreitol (1x LDS + 10% DTT) for 5 min at 96 °C. Forty microliters of each sample were transferred to gels (Thermo, USA) for the separation of proteins by their mass using electrophoresis. The proteins were blotted on a membrane, which was then transferred to *Rotti-Block-Solution* (Carl Roth, Germany) containing the primary murine antibodies targeting β -actin, and one of the target proteins (catalase, HO-1, or IL8; all SantaCruz, USA). After washing, labeling with secondary antibodies (anti-mouse antibody conjugated to horseradish peroxidase, HRP; SantaCruz, USA) was performed. Signal detection was done using 5-amino-2,3-dihydro-1,4-phthalazine dione (luminol) enhancer and stable peroxide SuperSignal (both ThermoFisher, USA). HRP-mediated catalysis of luminol to its oxidized form was quantified by detecting the luminescence emitted in this reaction (ImageQuant LAS 4000; GE Healthcare, Switzerland). For the analysis of IL8 and HO-1 in cell culture supernatants 24h after plasma treatment, commercially available IL8 and HO-1 ELISAs were used according to the manufacturer's instructions (IL8: BioLegend, UK; HO-1: Abcam; UK), and absolute concentrations were obtained against a known standard.

F. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was done using prism 8.4 (GraphPad Software, USA), using t-test or analysis of variances.

III. RESULTS

A. Jurkat cells were most sensitive to argon plasma while THP-1 cells were most sensitive to He/O₂ plasma

Modulating the feed gas composition of plasma jets changes their reactive species output in terms of composition and concentration. Details on the specific ROS and RNS output concerning the different feed gas compositions used were outlined previously [35, 37, 41, 45-54]. To identify the most cytotoxic feed gas composition in human leukemia cells, plasma treatment was performed (**Fig. 1a**), and the metabolic activity was assessed 4 h after treatment (**Fig. 1b**). At 2 slm, argon plasma treatment showed the highest toxicity in Jurkat cells with significant differences when compared to all of the other gas conditions employed in this study (**Fig. 1c**). By contrast, the He/O₂ conditions at 2 slm gave the most substantial decrease in the THP-1 cells' metabolic activity (**Fig. 1d**). At lower feed gas fluxes of 0.5 slm and 1.0 slm, similar tendencies

were observed in both cell lines, although not all comparisons reached statistical significance. This result is remarkable because it shows one cell line being most sensitive to one plasma-derived ROS composition, while a second cell line showed the sharpest decline in metabolic activity to another, chemically less related ROS composition. This is interesting also because the cell lines were both of leukemic origin. To further test the mode of cell death, cells were stained for the apoptosis marker of activated caspases 3 and 7. In Jurkat cells, apoptosis was induced at a high degree while that of THP-1 cells was less pronounced at 6 h following plasma treatment (**Fig. 1e**). As we wanted to identify the molecular basis of plasma-induced changes in subsequent experiments, we added another cell line to our experiments. The SK-MEL-28 (SKM) melanoma cells were also sensitive to argon plasma (**Fig. 1f**) and He/O₂ plasma treatment (**Fig. 1g**), and the decrease in metabolic activity was overall similar to that of THP-1 but not Jurkat cells.

B. HMOX1 was commonly upregulated in three plasma-treated cancer cell lines

Plasmas generate a plethora of ROS that are not only cytotoxic but also have signaling functions. Hence, it seemed plausible to screen the expression of redox-related proteins that, in principle, may be engaged by intracellular changes in the redox environment. To this end, we first performed a baseline expression of transcripts of 20 redox-related proteins in Jurkat, SKM, and THP-1 cells (**Fig. 2a**). Their functions were previously described [55]. For protein disulfide isomerase family A member 2 (PDIA2), nucleoredoxin (NXN), glutaredoxin 1 (GLRX1), and GLRX3, the expression was either absent, below the detection limit, or not detected because of the primers not binding properly to the target transcripts. Additionally, SKM cells were void of peroxiredoxin 2 (PRDX2) mRNA, suggesting either a mutated sequence or an absence of PRDX2 in these cells. To condense the data further, relative expression intensities were normalized to that of the most sensitive cell line in our study, Jurkat cells (**Fig. 2b**). Statistical analysis identified many significant differences at ± 2 -fold change levels. The THP-1 cells had significantly higher levels of the oxidoreductase and chaperone P4HB. In comparison, SKM cells had significantly higher levels in thioredoxin reductase 1 (TXNRD1) protecting from oxidative stress, NAD(P)H dehydrogenase quinone 1 (NQO1) regulating ubiquitin-independent p53 degradation and preventing oxidative stress, and heme oxygenase 1 (HMOX1) important in heme catabolism and generating anti-inflammatory carbon monoxide. To identify the regulatory role of plasma treatment in the expression of the 20 redox-regulated genes, the three cell types were exposed to either argon or He/O₂ plasma. At 4 h, gene expression was identified using qPCR screening, and values were normalized to these of each respective untreated cells. Again, many significant changes were observed, but only those showing a ± 2 -fold increase or decrease were labeled. In Jurkat cells, argon plasma treatment significantly increased thioredoxin (TXN) and HMOX1 expression and decreased TXNRD1 copy numbers (**Fig. 3a**). For He/O₂, also ERP27 (Endoplasmic Reticulum Protein 27) and NRF2 (nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2) regulating the expression of antioxidant proteins such as HMOX1, were significantly

Figure 3. Only HMOX1 was commonly regulated upon plasma treatment across the three different cell lines investigated. (a-c) control-normalized gene expression of transcripts coding for 20 redox-related proteins in Jurkat (a), SKM (b), and THP-1 cells (c) at 4 h following treatment (30 s) with either argon or He/O₂ plasma. Data represent mean and S.E. of two independent experiments; statistical analysis was performed using two-way analysis of variances, and is shown only for gene expression above the threshold of ± 2 -fold of expression in untreated (control) cells; * = $p < 0.05$, ** = $p < 0.01$, *** = $p < 0.001$; n.d. = none determined, ctrl = control.

upregulated. In SKM cells, argon plasma treatment significantly increased ERP27 and decreased TXNRD1 expression, while He/O₂ also increased the number of HMOX1 transcripts (Fig. 3b). In THP-1 cells, argon treatment significantly upregulated ERP44 and HMOX1, with the latter also being observed with He/O₂ treatment (Fig. 3c). These data provided evidence that several redox-regulated protein transcripts were part of the oxidative stress response evoked by plasma treatment. Of the 13 significant changes observed, five related to HMOX1. HMOX1 was the only gene showing a consistent increase in all three cell types and the two feed gas conditions investigated.

C. Knockdown of HO-1 and IL8 augmented the plasma-mediated cytotoxicity

The qPCR screen identified HMOX1 as a collective response element to plasma treatment. We next aimed at siRNA-mediated knockdown to understand its putative role in cytotoxic responses to plasma treatment. The protein of HMOX1, heme oxygenase 1 (HO-1) is co-expressed with catalase [56] and chemokine interleukin 8 (IL8) [57] whose expression was knocked down as well.

Figure 4. Determination of IC20 treatment times and confirmation of target protein knockdown using siRNA. (a, b) Jurkat (a) and THP-1 (b) cells were exposed to argon plasma treatment or argon gas control (Jurkat: 60 s; THP-1: 120 s), before assessing their metabolic activity and IC20 (Jurkat: 5 s; THP-1: 30 s) at 24 h; (c, d) validation of protein knockdown via siRNA in Jurkat (c) and THP-1 (d) cells for the proteins HO-1, catalase, and IL8. Data represent mean and S.E. or are representative of two independent experiments. Mock = transfection without target siRNA, NTC = non-targeting control (luciferase), HO-1 = heme oxygenase 1 protein, IL8 = interleukin 8, Ar = argon gas only control. MW are 42kDa (actin), 14 kDa (HO-1), 58 kDa (catalase), 11 kDa (IL8).

Catalase decomposes H_2O_2 , an oxidant frequently observed as a long-lived product in plasma-treated liquids. IL8 appeared attractive because of its 40-fold higher expression in THP-1 cells as compared to Jurkat cells [58]. The SKM melanoma cells were omitted because we could not apply the same transfection protocol as used for Jurkat and THP-1 cells. Only argon plasma treatment was used to reduce the number of iterations. To allow for comparison of reduction rates in metabolic activity, the plasma treatment time decreasing the metabolic activity by 20% (IC20) was identified in Jurkat cells being 5 s (Fig. 4a) and THP-1 cells being 30 s (Fig. 4b). Treatment with argon gas alone (plasma: off) showed no effect. The knockdown efficiency of the target proteins was confirmed 24 h after transfection in Jurkat (Fig. 4c) and THP-1 cells (Fig. 4d) via Western Blot.

Next, the effect of plasma treatment was identified 24 h after exposure. Several conditions were used, including untreated (not transfected, not plasma-treated), mock transfected

(transfection, but without siRNA), non-targeting control (NTC) transfected (transfected with siRNA but targeting a non-existing target in cells, the enzyme luciferase), and the target transfection with siRNA inhibiting either HMOX1, catalase (CAT), or IL8 (Fig. 5). The metabolic activity was normalized to that of untreated cells. Each of the procedures (the transfection, the insertion of siRNA, and the plasma treatment) has its individual degree of cytotoxic effect that cumulates when several of the procedures are combined, as shown for Jurkat cells (Fig. 5a). To compare any additive or synergistic effect of the plasma treatment and the transfection with the target, the mean decrease in metabolic activity is given in yellow numbers. The sum of the single treatments (plasma, and transfection with target siRNA) is shown in parentheses (e.g., for HMOX1: plasma 17.6% plus HMOX1 without plasma 21.5% equals 39.1%), to allow comparison against the combination treatment (plasma and transfection with siRNA targeting HMOX1 being 44.6%). This way, we identified the knockdown of HMOX1 (to a minor extent) and IL8 (to a major

extent) but not catalase to yield elevated toxicity in plasma-treated Jurkat cells. This was confirmed for HMOX1 and IL8 by flow cytometry, assessing the distribution of DAPI as an indicator of terminally dead Jurkat cells (Fig. 5b). In plasma-treated THP-1 cells, suppression of each of the targets led to a

more pronounced synergistic decrease in metabolic activity, with HMOX1 knockdown doubling the cytotoxic plasma effect (Fig. 5c). This was confirmed for HMOX1 and IL8 by flow cytometry, assessing the distribution of DAPI as an indicator of terminally dead THP-1 cells (Fig. 5d).

Figure 5. The knockdown of HO-1 and IL8 exacerbated the cytotoxicity of plasma treatment in leukemia cells. (a, b) decrease of metabolic activity normalized to untreated cells (a) and flow cytometry (b) of terminally dead (DAPI⁺) at 24 h of Jurkat cells either left untreated (untr.) or transfected without (mock) and with a siRNA targeting a non-expressed mRNA (non-targeting control, NTC = luciferase) or target (HMOX1, CAT, IL8) transcript with or without subsequent exposure to argon plasma; (c, d) metabolic activity (c) and flow cytometry (d) of terminally dead (DAPI⁺) at 24 h of THP-1 cells either left untreated (untr.) or transfected without (mock) and with a siRNA targeting a non-expressed mRNA (non-targeting control, NTC = luciferase) or target (HMOX1, CAT, IL8) transcript with or without subsequent exposure to argon plasma. Data represent mean and S.E. of four experiments with yellow numbers (a, c) indicating the mean of each bar, and the yellow numbers in parentheses indicating the sum of the reduction via plasma alone (blue graphs) and each of the targets without plasma treatment. The arrows point to the relevant comparisons. HO-1 = heme oxygenase 1 protein, IL8 = interleukin 8, CAT = catalase.

D. IL8 receptor blockage augmented HO-1 and partially IL8 secretion as well as plasma-induced cytotoxicity in leukemia cells.

Of the three targets investigated, knockdown of IL8 showed the most substantial effects in the two leukemia cell lines investigated. The chemokine CXCL8 (IL8) is usually released into the extracellular space where it can bind to its receptors, CD181 (CXCR1) and CD182 (CXCR2), on cells. Both receptors were highly expressed on both Jurkat and THP-1 cells (**Fig. 6a**). As the knockdown of IL8 provided increased cytotoxicity with plasma treatment, we hypothesized IL8 to act as a pro-survival signal that might be correlated with increased IL8-receptor expression in response to plasma-induced oxidative stress. To our surprise, both CD181 and CD182 were significantly downregulated in the viable (DAPI⁻) cell fraction 24h after plasma treatment in both Jurkat (**Fig. 6b**) and THP-1 (**Fig. 6c**) cells. To vice versa test the effect of exogenous recombinant IL8 and IL8-receptor (CD181/CD181) blockage, Jurkat and THP-1 cells pre-incubated with IL8 or anti CD181/CD182 antibodies, exposed to plasma, incubated for 24h, and analyzed for cell viability. Jurkat viability declined with antibody treatment to a greater extent compared to plasma exposure alone (**Fig. 6e**), while IL8 neither rescued nor elevated plasma-induced cell death (**Fig. 6f**). Additive cytotoxicity of the antibody treatment was even more pronounced in THP-1 cells (**Fig. 6g**), while the addition of IL8 here also failed to change the amplitude of plasma-induced cytotoxicity (**Fig. 6h**). The IL8-receptor blockage also induced a significantly increased IL8 release in THP-1 but not Jurkat cells, which was further elevated with plasma treatment (**Fig. 6i**). For HO-1, a significant increase in its secretion levels was found with IL8 receptor blockage in both untreated Jurkat (**Fig. 6j**) and THP-1 cells (**Fig. 6k**). Plasma treatment, however, did not elevate HO-1 secretion in either of the cell types, while the addition of IL8 decreased HO-1 release in Jurkat and increased HO-1 release in THP-1 cell, although to a minor extent.

IV. DISCUSSION

In the present study, we aimed at identifying both the most cytotoxic plasma feed gas composition and the molecular basis of plasma-mediated cytotoxicity in a proof-of-concept study using two leukemia cell lines. Overall, Jurkat cells were more sensitive to plasma-induced cell death compared to THP-1 cells. Argon (but not He/O₂) plasma treatment showed the most substantial toxicity against Jurkat, whereas He/O₂ (but not argon) plasma treatment showed the strongest toxicity in THP-1 cells. Knockdown of the proteins HO-1 and IL8, as well as IL8-receptor blockage, augmented cytotoxic plasma effects in both cell lines, suggesting a positive feedback loop between ROS-induced HO-1 expression, IL8 release, and binding of IL8 to IL8 receptors providing pro-survival signaling.

IL8 is a chemokine alarming leukocytes to infiltrate inflamed tissues [59, 60]. It is produced by several types of cells, including immune cells [61, 62] and stromal cells [63, 64], and induces calcium signaling and leukocyte maturation [65, 66] as well as angiogenesis [67]. Oxidative stress, as induced by plasma-derived ROS, increases IL8 secretion in many cell

types, including dendritic cells [68], endothelial cells [67], and monocytes [69]. With plasma treatment, we have recently shown an increase of IL8 mRNA and release in THP-1 monocytes [70], even up to 4 days after treatment [71]. Plasma treatment also increases IL8 production in human keratinocytes [72, 73]. As a mechanism, an intracellular loss of potassium with subsequent MAPK/ERK activation is discussed that governs the IL8 secretory response upon plasma treatment [74]. Increased IL8 release has also been observed in plasma-treated human neutrophils [75] and ovarian cancer cells [15]. While there is ample evidence supporting the oxidative stress-dependent IL8 release in human cells, studies describing its mechanism of making cells more resilient to ROS-induced cell death, as shown in our study, are scarce. Besides MAPK-regulation, IL8 promoter hyperacetylation is suggested as one mechanism of action in response to oxidative stress [76]. Another frequently mentioned link between oxidative stress and IL8 release is the protein heme oxygenase 1 (HO-1) that can be activated through the transcription factor nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2 (Nrf2), eventually facilitating potent antioxidant responses [77].

The suppression of HO-1 potentiated plasma-mediated cytotoxic effects in our study. Vice versa, HO-1 was shown to extensively promote resistance to oxidative stress and protection from ROS-induced damage [78, 79]. The primary role of HO-1 is to degrade heme, thereby generating iron, biliverdin, and carbon monoxide [80]. While the importance of HO-1 in antioxidant defense in health and disease is undisputed [77], it is clear that cell cultures do not contain significant amounts of heme as in blood, making the exact mechanism of protection *in vitro* to remain largely elusive as of now. The mRNA of HO-1, HMOX1, is found to be frequently upregulated in response to oxidative stress in general and plasma treatment specifically. Underlining the results of this study, we have recently identified HMOX1 to serve as a common response element to plasma-induced oxidative stress in eight human cancer cell lines [14]. We found the target not only to be increased in plasma-treated monocytes [70] and keratinocytes [81] but also in plasma-treated acute wounds in mice, showing a 200-fold increase as compared to untreated wounds [3]. These data warrant more research on HMOX1 / HO-1 expression being clear indicators for signaling responses to plasma-derived ROS in plasma medicine.

Another presumably obvious target to investigate is catalase. The enzyme detoxifies H₂O₂ at compelling rate constants [82] but is restricted primarily to peroxisomes in cells. With plasma-derived ROS unlikely diffusing through several cell membranes and the cytosol without losing reactivity at the biomolecules present [33], the importance of this enzyme in plasma medicine is maybe overstated. It is also proposed that not the total levels of catalase but its location on the membrane might be decisive for antitumor plasma effects [83, 84]. Nevertheless, knockdown of catalase increased plasma-induced cytotoxicity in THP-1 cells to some extent in our study. One hypothesis might be that both HO-1 and catalase not only protect from plasma-derived ROS but also ROS being produced endogenously by the cells following plasma treatment. Several studies have mentioned endogenous ROS production in response to plasma exposure [85, 86].

Figure 6. IL8 receptor blockage augmented HO-1 and partially IL8 secretion as well as plasma-induced cytotoxicity in leukemia cells. (a-d) representative overlay histograms of the fluorescence intensities of labeled CD181 and CD182 on viable (DAPI-) Jurkat cells (a) and quantification thereof (b), and DAPI- THP-1 cells (c) and quantification thereof (d) at 24 h following plasma treatment; (e-f) representative dot-plot of the forward scatter (FSC, size) and the fluorescence intensity of caspase 3/7 activation in Jurkat cells indicative of apoptosis (e) and quantification of the percentage of viable cells in samples pre-incubated for 24h with either vehicle, recombinant IL8 (100ng/ml), or anti CD181/182 antibodies (f); (g-h) representative dot-plot of the forward scatter (FSC, size) and the fluorescence intensity of caspase 3/7 activation in THP-1 cells indicative of apoptosis (g) and quantification of the percentage of viable cells in samples pre-incubated for 24h with either vehicle, recombinant IL8 (100ng/ml), or anti CD181/182 antibodies (h); (i-k) IL8 (i) and HO-1 (j-k) ELISA performed from the supernatants of the cells presented in f and h. Data represent mean and S.E. of two to four independent experiments; statistical analysis was performed using t-test; * = $p < 0.05$, ** = $p < 0.01$, *** = $p < 0.001$; ctrl = control, unst. = unstained.

At higher concentrations, ROS damage cells, leading to their demise. However, it is currently unclear whether the types or amounts of ROS or both govern their cytotoxic responses. For instance, different cell types may have different sensitivities to the ROS-induced cell death, independent of the type of ROS being used. We here provide evidence for the opposite case. The argon plasma regimen is rich in the generation of hydroxyl radicals [87], ultimately decomposing to H₂O₂. By contrast, the He/O₂ condition was proposed to be rich in atomic and singlet delta oxygen [88, 89], with the former facilitating the generation of hypochlorous acid [38], provided extensive disturbances do not lead to quenching via ambient-air derived oxygen to ozone [51]. Using a different plasma jet than the kINPen, we have previously established the high sensitivity of THP-1 cells to He/O₂ plasma [40]. For Jurkat T-lymphocytes, we expected a similar tendency. However, He/O₂ plasma was among the least cytotoxic condition in Jurkat cells, while argon plasma showed the highest efficacy. By contrast, all helium plasma conditions were more cytotoxic in THP-1 cells as compared to the argon plasma treatment. These results drastically change our view of ROS-induced cell death in plasma medicine and in redox biology. While several studies [90-92], including our own [6, 14, 23, 44, 93], have identified some cell lines to more susceptible to plasma treatment over others, using different plasma-derived ROS compositions might have yielded opposite effects, as suggested with our results observed here in Jurkat and THP-1 cells. The broader implications of these findings remain to be established but it can be hypothesized that tumors unresponsive to one type of plasma might become responsive when changing the ROS composition in the very same device. Hence, it can be claimed that identifying optimal ROS compositions for each of the targeted tumor entities is a challenge that only has started to be tackled in the field of plasma medicine.

Plasma treatment led to a significant decrease in the expression in the surface receptors CXCR1 (CD181) and CXCR2 (CD182) known to bind IL8 [94]. This might be due to the oxidation-induced change of epitopes, and subsequent differences in antibody binding. However, it is more likely that this downregulation is a consequence of a response to stimulus, as both CD181 and CD182 are rapidly internalized and recycled upon target binding to allow desensitization to IL8 for migrating along the chemokine gradient in tissues [95]. Our data are in line with this as plasma treatment induced a slight (Jurkat) and prominent (THP-1) induction of IL8 release, which in turn leads to internalization of the receptors. However, CD181/CD182 expression can also be modulated in response to infection [96]. CXCR2 is moreover upregulated in many types of cancers to sustain inflammation and promote growth through the binding of several CXCL-ligands [97]. CD181/CD182 blockage with antibodies significantly augmented the plasma-induced cell death in both leukemia lines tested. This validates the importance of the CXCL8-axis in the survival of these cells in response to plasma-induced oxidative stress, a conclusion also drawn in previous studies on chemoresistance using human prostate cancer cells [98, 99]. Interestingly, both untreated and plasma-treated THP-1 cells attempted to counteract on the lack of autocrine IL8 stimulation due to the IL8R-blockage by increasing the production of IL8 more than 20-fold. In the combination with the massively elevated cell death observed

with anti-CD181/CD182 treatment and siRNA-mediated IL8 knockdown, our functional data suggest the autocrine IL8 stimulation to be of so far unreported relevance in the coping of plasma-induced oxidative stress *in vitro*.

Heme oxygenase 1 (HO-1) undoubtedly is relevant in health in disease [100, 101]. The consequences of its regulation, however, are not linear, since modest upregulation is associated with antioxidative activity and cytoprotection while higher levels even promote ROS production [102, 103]. In human monocytes, HO-1 upregulation results in decrease TNF α and ROS levels, and increased SOD expression [104]. In oncology, it is known that HO-1 expression increases angiogenesis, chemoresistance, and protects from apoptosis [105]. Hence, the substantial increase in cell death observed in HO-1 knockdown experiments was not surprising, while the role of IL8 in such setting is less clear. This is further complicated as IL8 release depends on other factors, such as HIF-1 α attenuating Nrf2-dependent IL8 production. Nevertheless, expression of IL8 is independent on that of HO-1[57]. Our data hence suggest that co-suppression of both HO-1 and IL-8 might further amplify plasma-induced toxicity. The therapeutic relevance of this, however, remains to be established.

V. CONCLUSION

In our proof-of-concept study using two leukemia cell lines, the plasma-induced cytotoxicity depended on both the cell type investigated and the ROS-mixtures generated. While the exact mechanisms of cells succumbing to plasma-induced cell death remain elusive, we provide evidence that both heme oxygenase 1 and interleukin 8, as well as autocrine stimulation via the two IL8-receptors, promote the survival of plasma-treated cells. Further research is warranted to understand the broader implications of these findings in the fields of plasma medicine and plasma onco-therapy.

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VII. REFERENCES

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